

EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF PERSONALITY TRAITS ON DECISION MAKING AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS: MODERATING ROLE OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

^{*1}Muhammad Ilyas, ²Masooma Ali, ³Urooj Bibi
¹⁻³Riphah International University Islamabad, Pakistan

DOI:

Keywords:

Personality Traits, Decision Making Styles, Emotional Intelligence, University Students

Article History

Received on 29 Dec, 2025

Accepted on 24 Jan, 2026

Published on 26 Jan, 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Decisions Making styles are varying from person to person, often shaped by one's personality traits. However, emotional intelligence (EI) may also play a moderating role. The present study examined the impact of personality traits on decision-making styles among university students, considering EI as a moderator. A cross-sectional survey was conducted at Riphah International University Malakand Campus using a sample of 256 students selected through Taro Yamani's formula. Standardized instruments, including the Big Five Inventory, Decision Style Inventory, and Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS), were used. Results revealing that openness showed positive correlation with extroversion ($r = .35$), and agreeableness ($r = .29$), while conscientiousness was also positively associated with several traits. Regarding decision-making styles, directive style correlated with neuroticism ($r=.15$) and openness ($r=.30$), analytical with openness ($r=.29$), and conceptual was negatively correlated with neuroticism ($r = -.14$). WLEIS showed strong correlations with openness ($r = .48$) and several decision styles including directive ($r = .38$), analytical ($r = .37$), and behavioral ($r = .29$). WLEIS showed negative correlations with conscientiousness ($r = -.14$), conceptual ($r = -.29$), and directive ($r = -.42$) styles. However, moderation analysis revealed no significant interaction effects except a weak moderation of EI between conscientiousness and directive style ($p = .048$). Findings suggest that while EI enhances decision-making, it does not significantly alter personality-driven effects. These findings support the development of interventions aimed at enhancing EI to improve decision making among university students.

Introduction

In today's complex and evolving social and academic environment, students make decisions that significantly affect their academic, professional, and personal lives. These range from everyday problem-solving to major life choices, which are largely influenced by individual differences, particularly personality traits. Research indicates that decision-making styles are shaped by personality traits, which affect how individuals perceive information and handle challenges (Othman et al., 2020). Emotional awareness and regulation also influence decision-making, highlighting that it is not purely a cognitive process (Yilmaz, 2023). Emotional intelligence, the ability to identify, understand, and manage emotions, may moderate the impact of personality traits on decision outcomes (Martínez-Rodríguez & Ferreira, 2025). Accordingly, this study examines the relationship between personality traits and decision-making styles among undergraduate students, with a focus on the moderating role of emotional intelligence.

Personality encompasses enduring psychological attributes that govern how individuals think, feel, and behave across situations (Bleidorn et al., 2021). The Big Five model; openness, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism—offers a robust framework for understanding individual differences (Marengo et al., 2021). These traits help explain why some individuals prefer directive or analytical decision-making styles, whereas others adopt conceptual or interpersonal approaches (Babakr & Fatahi, 2023). Similarly, Jung's (1923) typological theory emphasizes perception and judgment as key determinants of behavior.

Personality alone, however, may not fully account for variations in decision-making. Emotional intelligence has been shown to enhance thoughtful and contextually appropriate decisions, particularly under stress (Martínez-Rodríguez & Ferreira, 2025). This construct, increasingly recognized in psychology, facilitates self-regulation, empathy, and effective communication (Raeissi et al., 2019), allowing individuals to perceive, understand, manage, and apply emotions adaptively (Aziz et al., 2020). Combined with personality traits, emotional intelligence can either amplify or attenuate the influence of personality on decision-making among university students.

Effective decision-making is critical for university students, impacting academic success, career trajectories, and personal growth (Aziz et al., 2020). Students often face inconsistent decision-making quality; poor decisions can lead to academic setbacks, interpersonal conflicts,

and long-term dissatisfaction (Rajbhandari et al., 2023). These differences in decision-making styles are influenced by personality traits and cognitive processes (Noor & Abid, 2022). Consequently, understanding the interplay between personality and emotional intelligence is essential for explaining why students differ in their decision-making approaches.

The trait-based approach has consistently demonstrated that personality shapes decision-making patterns (Khalisah, 2023). Conscientiousness, characterized by organization and goal-orientation, is linked to rational and methodical decisions (Kropf, 2025), while neuroticism, associated with emotional instability, may lead to avoidant or impulsive decision-making (Bayram & Aydemir, 2017). Jungian typology further clarifies decision tendencies: introversion/extraversion, thinking/feeling, and sensing/intuition preferences relate to logical, value-driven, or intuitive decision-making (Jung, 1923; Lee et al., 2022).

Empirical studies support these theoretical perspectives. Riaz et al. (2012) reported that personality explained 15.4% to 28.1% of variance in university students' decision-making. Doe et al. (2017) found that work-related personality traits influenced adaptive decision-making, while (Aziz et al., 2020) demonstrated that openness and extraversion affected career decisions. Although these studies highlight the importance of personality, they suggest additional factors, such as emotional intelligence, contribute to decision-making outcomes.

Emotional intelligence, initially proposed by Mayer and Salovey and later expanded by Shengyao et al. (2024), predicts adaptive behaviors across academic, occupational, and social contexts. It encompasses self-emotion appraisal, others' emotion appraisal, emotion regulation, and use of emotion (Elshaer et al., 2025). Individuals high in emotional intelligence manage stress effectively, empathize with others, and make informed decisions under pressure (Tung et al., 2024). Studies integrating emotional intelligence and personality show that it enhances rational and intuitive decision-making while reducing career decision difficulties (Othman et al., 2020; Dev & Arlı, 2025). However, most research treats these constructs independently, leaving the moderating role of emotional intelligence underexplored (Dong et al., 2022).

Decision-making assessment tools, such as the Decision Style Inventory, capture individual preferences across four dimensions: analytical, conceptual, directive, and behavioral (Scott & Bruce, 1995). Analytical decision-makers are data-oriented, conceptual thinkers are visionary, behavioral styles prioritize consensus, and directive styles emphasize quick, decisive

actions (Lee et al., 2022). Using these tools alongside the BFI-10 and WLEIS positions this study to contribute meaningfully to both theory and practice.

Although personality is associated with decision-making tendencies, emotional intelligence strengthens or attenuates these effects. Its moderating role, particularly among Pakistani university students, has not been rigorously examined. This study addresses this gap by exploring how emotional intelligence moderates the influence of personality traits on decision-making styles in students from District Malakand, Pakistan. Understanding this interaction has practical implications for educators, counselors, and administrators seeking to enhance self-awareness, responsible decision-making, and emotional competence. Additionally, conducting research in an underrepresented region extends the generalizability of findings and contributes to South Asian psychological literature.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the relationship between personality traits, decision-making styles and emotional intelligence among university students.
2. To investigate the moderating role of emotional intelligence in the relationship between personality traits and decision-making styles.

Hypotheses of the Study

H1: There is significant relationship between personality traits (extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness) and decision-making styles (directive, analytical, conceptual, and behavioral).

H2: Emotional Intelligence moderates the relationship of each personality trait and decision-making style among university students.

Methods

Research Design

The present study employed a cross-sectional survey research design using a quantitative approach for data collection and analysis.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Using simple random sampling technique, a sample of 256 university students was selected from entire population of 713 by using Taro Yamane's formula. The sample included both male and female students (52.3% were male and 47.7% were female) enrolled in different academic programs at Riphah International University, Malakand Campus, Khyber

Pakhtunkhwa. Students who were currently enrolled at the university level and willing to participate were included in the study. Participants with any reported mental or cognitive impairment were excluded.

Operational Definitions & Research Instruments

Personality Traits

Refers to the classification of individuals based on their characteristic patterns of thoughts, emotions, and behaviors. Personality traits were assessed by utilizing the Big Five Inventory; having 10 items, used for measuring five personality traits (extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness), two items for every trait with scoring on Likert form. The reliability of this inventory is Cronbach's $\alpha = .73$ (Rammstedt & John, 2007).

Emotional Intelligence

Emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive, understand, regulate, and use emotions effectively. Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale; having 16 items scored on Likert scale, reliability coefficient of ($\alpha = .94$) was used in the study for assessing emotional intelligence of the study participants (Wong & Law, 2002).

Decision Making Style

Decision-making style refers to how individuals approach choices. Decision Style Inventory; having 20 items and 4 sub-scales (directive, analytical, conceptual, behavioral), five items for every sub-scale was used in the study for assessing decision making style of the participants (Rowe et al., 1994). It demonstrated excellent reliability ($\alpha = .80$), with each of its four styles, directive, analytical, conceptual, and behavioral showing very high reliability scores ($\alpha = .96$ to $.99$).

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by Ethics committee of Riphah International University. Participants provided written informed consent; participation was voluntary and they could withdraw at any time without penalty. Data were stored securely, and confidentiality as well as anonymity of the participants were assured. Participants were also offered a summary of findings on request.

Results

The results aimed to investigate the relationship between personality traits, decision-making styles and emotional intelligence among university students. Furthermore, the moderating role

of emotional intelligence in the relationship between personality traits and decision-making styles was also examined.

Table 1: *Descriptive and Pearson Correlation of Personality Traits Decision Making Styles and Emotional Intelligence (n = 256)*

Variables	M	SD	a	k	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Extraversion	6.1	1.6	.50	02	~									
Agreeableness	6.1	2.1	.54	02	.18	~								
Conscientiousness	6.3	1.8	.51	02	.20**	.29**	~							
Neuroticism	6.6	2.5	.52	02	.10	.33**	.27**	~						
Openness	6.2	1.9	.64	02	.35**	.29**	.21**	.31**	~					
Directive Decision	68	48	.99	20	.01	.10	-.09	.15*	.30**	~				
Analytical Decision	49	17	.96	20	.07	.13*	.01	.07	.29**	.40**	~			
Conceptual Decision	50	13	.97	20	-.08	-.05	-.05	-.14*	-.29**	-.57**	-.66**	~		
Behavioral Decision	52	22	.98	20	.01	-.12*	.05	-.10	-.34**	-.77**	-.68**	.45**	~	
WLEIS	48	16	.94	16	.08	.07	-.14*	.05	.48**	.38**	.37**	-.29**	-.42**	~

Note: M = Mean, SD = Standard Deviation, k = No. of items, a = Cronbach's alpha, WLEIS = Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale, **p < .01, ***p < .001.

Table 1 presents means, standard deviations, internal consistency reliabilities, and Pearson correlations among personality traits, decision-making styles, and emotional intelligence (N = 256). Cronbach's alpha values ranged from .50 to .99, indicating acceptable to excellent reliability. Several significant correlations were observed among personality traits, decision-making styles, and emotional intelligence, with correlation coefficients ranging from -.77 to .48 (p < .05 to p < .01).

Table 2: *Moderation of Emotional Intelligence Between Personality Traits and Decision-Making Style*

Variables	Model 1			Model 2		
	B	β	SE	B	β	SE
Constant	22***		1.9	22***		1.9
BFI	.03	.19	1.9	.03	.10	2.0
WLEIS	11***	.34***	1.9	11***	.34***	2.2
BFI* WLEIS				.39	.01	1.9

R ²	.14	.14
Δ R ²		.000

Note: N= 256, BFI= Big Five Inventory, WLEIS= Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale, ***p < .001.

Table 2 shows moderation of emotional intelligence between personality traits and decision-making styles. In model 1, the value of R² is .14 which indicates that the predictors explained 14% variance in the outcome with $F(2, 252) = 21.0, p < .001$. In model 2, the value of R² is also .14 shows that the predictors explained 14% variance in the outcome with $F(3, 251) = 13.99, p < .001$.

Table 3: Moderation Analysis of Emotional Intelligence on the Relationship between Conscientiousness and Directive Decision Making Style

	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p
			Lower	Upper		
BFLC	.24	.73	-1.2	1.6	0.3	.736
WLEIS	-.58	.07	-0.7	-0.4	-7.9	<.001
BFI_C * WLEIS	.08	.04	6.6	0.1	1.9	.048

Note: BFI_C= Conscientiousness, WLEIS= Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale, ***p < .001.

Table 3 presents the moderation analysis examining the interaction between conscientiousness and emotional intelligence in predicting directive decision-making style. Emotional intelligence was a significant predictor ($\beta = -0.59, p < .001$), and the interaction term was statistically significant ($\beta = 0.08, p = .048$), indicating a moderation effect.

Table 4: Conditional Effects of Moderating Variable on the Relationship Between Conscientiousness and Directive Decision Making Style (DSI_D)

	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p
			Lower	Upper		
Average	0.2	0.7	-1.2	1.7	0.3	.732
Low (-1SD)	-1.2	0.8	-2.9	0.5	-1.3	.167
High (+1SD)	1.7	1.2	-0.6	4.0	1.4	.152

Table 4 displays the conditional effects of conscientiousness on directive decision-making style at low (-1 SD), average, and high (+1 SD) levels of emotional intelligence. None of the conditional effects were statistically significant ($p > .05$).

Figure 1

Table 5: Moderation Analysis of Emotional Intelligence on the Relationship Between Personality Traits and Decision-Making Styles

		95% Confidence Interval					
		β	SE	Lower	Upper	Z	p
DSI_A	BFI_E * WLEIS	1.1	.11	-.28	.15	-.58	.558
	BFI_A * WLEIS	1.0	.07	-.13	.17	.24	.810
	BFI_C * WLEIS	1.1	.09	-.33	.05	-.40	.161
	BFI_N * WLEIS	1.0	.08	-.07	.25	1.1	.263
	BFI_O * WLEIS	0.8	.06	-.11	.14	.28	.775
DSI_B	BFI_E * WLEIS	0.3	.04	-.13	.03	-1.2	.229
	BFI_A * WLEIS	0.4	.02	-.07	.04	-.55	.582
	BFI_C * WLEIS	0.4	.03	-.13	.00	-1.7	.081
	BFI_N * WLEIS	0.4	.03	-.11	.01	-1.5	.114
	BFI_O * WLEIS	0.3	.02	-.05	.03	-.48	.631
DSI_C	BFI_E * WLEIS	0.2	.03	-.05	.07	.23	.813

	BFI_A * WLEIS	-0.2	.02	-.03	.05	.30	.760
	BFI_C * WLEIS	-0.2	.02	-.04	.06	.27	.781
	BFI_N * WLEIS	-0.2	.02	-.03	.05	.34	.730
	BFI_O * WLEIS	-0.1	.01	-.01	.06	1.2	.195
DSI_D	BFI_E * WLEIS	-0.5	.05	-.10	.09	-.05	.952
	BFI_A * WLEIS	-0.5	.03	-.04	.09	.70	.480
	BFI_N * WLEIS	-0.5	.03	-.07	.07	-.08	.933
	BFI_O * WLEIS	-0.4	.02	-.08	.03	-.82	.409

Note: BFI = Big Five Inventory, DSI = Decision Style Inventory, WLEIS = Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale, BFI_E = Extraversion, BFI_A = Agreeableness, BFI_C = Conscientiousness, BFI_N = Neuroticism and BFI_O = Openness, DSI_D = Directive decision style, DSI_A = Analytical decision style, DSI_C = Conceptual decision style, DSI_B = Behavioural decision style.

Table 5 presents the results of nineteen moderation analyses examining emotional intelligence as a moderator between personality traits and decision-making styles. None of the interaction terms were statistically significant ($p > .05$), indicating no moderating effect of emotional intelligence in these models.

Discussion

The present study investigated the relationships between personality traits, decision-making styles, and emotional intelligence among university students. Additionally, the moderating role of emotional intelligence in the relationship between personality traits and decision-making styles was examined.

Consistent with the first hypothesis, openness was positively correlated with analytical decision-making style. This suggests that individuals who are imaginative, intellectually curious, and receptive to new ideas tend to engage in structured, information-driven decision processes. These findings align with Fabio et al. (2015), who reported that high-openness individuals embrace complexity and exhibit thoughtful decision-making patterns. Similarly, Lee et al. (2022) found that open individuals are adaptive and methodical when faced with novel or complex choices. Interestingly, openness was negatively associated with conceptual and behavioral decision-making styles. While high-openness individuals favor rational analysis, they may be less inclined toward abstract, futuristic decisions (conceptual style) or emotionally oriented, relationship-focused approaches (behavioral style). Comparable insights have been reported by

(Kropf, 2025), suggesting that directive and behavioral decision-makers operate best within structured frameworks, whereas those high in openness thrive in flexible, idea-rich environments.

Conscientiousness demonstrated positive correlations with extraversion and agreeableness, indicating that organized and responsible individuals often display cooperative and socially engaging tendencies. This is consistent with the work of Khalisah (2023), which highlights conscientiousness as a predictor of socially desirable behaviors. However, contrary to prior research linking conscientiousness with systematic and logical decision-making (B. P. Allen, 2015b), this study found a non-significant or weakly negative association with analytical decision-making (Dev & Arlı, 2025b). This discrepancy may be due to contextual factors, including the academic environment and sociocultural expectations among Pakistani university students. In high-pressure or hierarchical academic settings, conscientious individuals may prioritize task completion and rule-following over in-depth analytical engagement, thereby influencing their decision preferences.

Other personality traits also showed distinct patterns. The findings suggest that while personality traits influence decision-making styles, the strength and direction of these associations vary, and some expected relationships were not observed, highlighting the role of contextual and cultural factors.

Regarding the second objective, it was hypothesized that emotional intelligence would moderate the relationship between personality traits and decision-making styles. Contrary to expectations, hierarchical moderation analyses indicated that emotional intelligence did not significantly moderate the overall relationships between the Big Five personality traits and any of the four decision-making styles (analytical, conceptual, directive, or behavioral) (Table 2). A marginal exception was observed for the interaction between conscientiousness and emotional intelligence on directive decision-making, suggesting a small moderation effect (Table 3). These findings contrast with previous research demonstrating the moderating influence of emotional intelligence on decision-making, such as Othman et al. (2020) and Dev and Arlı (2025), which reported that emotional intelligence enhanced adaptive decision-making styles.

The lack of significant moderation may be attributable to sample characteristics, where students relied primarily on personality-driven strategies rather than emotional intelligence when making decisions. Contextual factors, including academic demands, cultural norms, and

the nature of university decision-making tasks, may also diminish the moderating role of emotional intelligence.

Despite this, emotional intelligence showed significant direct correlations with analytical and behavioral decision-making styles, suggesting that students with higher emotional intelligence tend to adopt more strategic and collaborative approaches. This aligns with Tung et al. (2024), who emphasized the importance of emotional awareness in facilitating logical and group-centered decision-making.

Conclusion

Several limitations should be considered. First, the study sampled students from a single university in District Malakand, limiting generalizability across broader student populations. Second, reliance on self-report measures may introduce response biases. Third, the cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences. Future research should consider larger, more diverse samples and adopt longitudinal or mixed method approaches to more fully capture the dynamic interplay between personality traits, emotional intelligence, and decision-making behavior.

References

- Allen, B.P. (2015). *Personality Theories: Development, Growth, and Diversity* (5th ed.). Psychology Press. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315665115>
- Al-Hawtali, A. M., Zaib, K., & Al-Hossini, A. S. (2025). Voices in exile: Postcolonial identity and Muslim immigrant experience in Abdulrazak Gurnah's *Admiring Silence*. *Academy of Education and Social Sciences Review*, 5(4), 579-588.
- Aziz, A. R. A., Sulaiman, S., & Razak, N. H. A. (2020). Students' Emotional Intelligence and Self-efficacy towards Their Academic Performance: A Survey Study on Public Higher Learning Institution. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(11C), 129-135. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.082315>
- Babakr, Z. H., & Fatahi, N. (2023). Big five personality traits and risky decision-making: A study of behavioural tasks among college students. *Passer Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 5(2), 298-303. <https://doi.org/10.24271/psr.2023.387309.1263>
- Bayram, N., & Aydemir, M. (2017, August). Decision-making styles and personality traits. *International Journal of Recent Advances in Organizational Behaviour and Decision Sciences (IJRAOB)*, 3(1).

- Bleidorn, W., Hopwood, C. J., Back, M. D., Denissen, J. J. A., Hennecke, M., Hill, P. L., Jokela, M., Kandler, C., Lucas, R. E., Luhmann, M., Orth, U., Roberts, B. W., Wagner, J., Wrzus, C., & Zimmermann, J. (2021). *Personality trait stability and change*. *Personality Science*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5964/ps.6009>
- Dev, M. A., & Arli, N. B. (2025). The role of personality traits and decision-making styles in career decision-making difficulties. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(2), 159. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15020159>
- Doe, R., Castillo, M. S., & McKinney, A. B. (2017). Work personality and decision-making styles among working and non-working students. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 5, 286–297. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2017.56024>
- Dong, X., Kalugina, O. A., Vasbieva, D. G., & Rafi, A. (2022). Emotional intelligence and personality traits based on academic performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.894570>
- El Othman, R., Hallit, R., Obeid, S., & Hallit, S. (2020). Personality traits, emotional intelligence, and decision-making styles in Lebanese university medical students. *BMC Psychology*, 8, 46. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-020-00406-4>
- Elshaer, I. A., Sobaih, A. E. E., Alyahya, M., Azazz, A. M. S., & Khan, M. A. (2025). Unlocking potential: The impact of emotional intelligence on quality of life and academic success of students with disabilities. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2025.1659221>
- Khalisah, N. (2023). The role of emotional intelligence in effective decision-making. *Journal of Management and Administration Provision*, 3(1), 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.55885/jmap.v3i1.220>
- Kropf, M. (2025). Conscience and conscientiousness within surrogate decision-making: Philosophical considerations on the ethical relevance of conscientiousness. *Clinical Ethics*, 20(3), 146–157. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14777509251332328>
- Lee, S., Jung, J., Baek, S., & Lee, S. (2022). The relationship between career decision-making self-efficacy, career preparation behaviour and career decision difficulties among South Korean college students. *Sustainability*, 14(21), 14384. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114384>

- Marengo, D., Davis, K. L., & Gradwohl, G. Ö. (2021). A meta-analysis on individual differences in primary emotional systems and Big Five personality traits. *Scientific Reports*, 11, 7453. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-84366-8>
- Martínez-Rodríguez, A., & Ferreira, C. (2025b). Factors influencing the development of emotional intelligence in university students. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 40(2). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-025-00956-4>
- Noor, A., & Ch, A. (2022). Students' perception of decision-making styles at university level in Punjab. *Global Social Sciences Review*, 7, 421-429. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2022\(VII-II\).41](https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2022(VII-II).41)
- Raeissi, P., Zandian, H., & Mirzarahimy, T. (2019). Relationship between communication skills and emotional intelligence among nurses. *Nursing Management*. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nm.2019.e1820>
- Rajbhandari Vaidya, P., & Acharya, K. (2023). Students' decision-making at the university level: A phenomenological study. *Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5, 20-34. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jbmr.v5i1-2.58568>
- Rammstedt, B., & John, O. P. (2007). Measuring personality in one minute or less: A 10-item short version of the Big Five Inventory in English and German. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 41(1), 203-212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2006.02.001>
- Riaz, M. N., Riaz, M. A., & Batool, N. (2012). Personality types as predictors of decision-making styles. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 22(2).
- Shengyao, Y., Xuefen, L., Jenatabadi, N., Nadia, S., Ke, C., & Ishak, Z. (2024). Emotional intelligence impact on academic achievement and psychological well-being among university students: The mediating role of positive psychological characteristics. *BMC Psychology*, 12, 389. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-01886-4>
- Wong, C.-S., & Law, K. S. (2002). *Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS)* [Database record]. APA PsycTests. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t07398-000>
- Yılmaz, S. (2023). The relationship between emotional intelligence and decision-making. *Neuropsychiatric Investigation*, 61(4), 117-121. <https://doi.org/10.5152/NeuropsychiatricInvest.2023.23010>